

dichloride (25 ml) at 0–5° and the mixture was stirred for 10–15 min at that temperature. The imine (3; 10 mmol) was then added to it followed by dropwise addition of triethylamine (4.2 ml, 30 mmol) in methylene dichloride (15 ml). The resulting mixture was stirred overnight (20–24 h) at room temperature and then washed with water (100 ml). The organic layer was separated, dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent evaporated to give an oil which on treatment with ethanol yielded the β -lactams (4–11).

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Synthesis of a Dehydroretinol Congener

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3-Ethoxyanhydroretinol (4) is formed in high yield when 3-dehydroretinol (1) is treated with ethanolic hydrogen chloride^{1–4}. Variation of reaction conditions resulted in the formation of a number of compounds, one which viz. 3-ethoxyretroretinyl ethyl ether has already been described⁵. Here we report the synthesis of another 3-dehydroretinol congener, viz. 3-ethoxyretinyl ethyl ether (7) by the treatment of compound 1 with ethanolic hydrogen chloride (0.13 N) for 1.5 h.

The minced liver of *Bagarius bagarius* was extracted with light petroleum (b.p. 60–80°) as usual⁶. The reddish brown liver oil (2 g) so obtained ($\epsilon_{1\text{ cm}}^{1\%}$ at 345 nm = 144.6) dissolved in light petroleum (5 ml) was chromatographed on water-deactivated alumina column (5%, v/w). The dehydroretinyl ester (0.2365 g, $\epsilon_{1\text{ cm}}^{1\%}$ at 351 nm = 520) was collected and saponified with 10% (w/v) ethanolic KOH (100 ml) at 50–60° for 40 min. The unsaponifiable matter was extracted with light petroleum, dried and concentrated under reduced pressure. The resulting 3-dehydroretinol was

treated with dry ethanolic hydrogen chloride (0.13 N; 100 ml) and allowed to stand in dark at room temperature (30°) for 1.5 h. The reaction mixture was neutralised with sodium bicarbonate solution and extracted with light petroleum. The extract was washed, dried and finally concentrated to about 5 ml and chromatographed on water-deactivated alumina (5%, v/w). The fourth greenish-yellow zone was eluted with light petroleum containing 5% diethyl ether. On repeated chromatography, the single zone separated into two distinct yellow zones. The eluate was then collected and fractions having similar uv spectra were pooled together. The fraction was characterised as 3-ethoxyretroretinyl ethyl ether⁵. The second zone was also collected in fractions by elution with light petroleum containing 6% diethyl ether. Fractions having similar uv spectra were pooled together and rechromatographed for further purification. The purified compound (2.5 mg) showed a single spot on a silica gel plate (0.25 mm thick) with a solvent system of acetone–light petroleum (1 : 19, v/v), $R_f = 0.48$.

On the basis of chemical analysis and spectral evidences, structure 7 was assigned to the product, λ_{max} 328 (light petroleum) and 330 nm (ethanol); the SbCl_5 reaction gave λ_{max} 670 nm; ν_{max} 2 965, 2 925, 2 860, 1 450, 1 375, 1 275, 1 105 and 965 cm^{-1} ; δ (60 MHz; CCl_4) 1.0–1.6 (14H, m, 4- CH_2 and ring methylene protons at C-2), 1.7 (3H, s, ring allylic CH_3 at C-5), 1.9 (6H, s, 2- CH_3 in acyclic

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chain), 2.10 (2H, t, methylene protons at C-4), 3.70 (4H, m, deshielded methylene protons of ethoxy groups), 3.75 (1H, m, methine proton at C-3), 4.25 (2H, d, methylene protons at C-15) and 5.9–6.6 (6H, m, vinylic protons at C-7, C-8, C-10, C-11, C-12 and C-14); M^+ value at m/z 358, $C_{24}H_{38}O_2$.

3-Ethoxyretinyl ethyl ether was converted into the corresponding hydroxy compound⁵. This compound also showed λ_{max} at 328 nm (light petroleum); the $SbCl_5$ reaction product gave λ_{max} 670 nm; ν_{max} 3 320 cm^{-1} (OH).

It has been observed that a number of compounds is formed when 3-dehydroretinol is treated with dry ethanolic hydrogen chloride¹⁻³. The compound reported here has been proved to be 3-ethoxyretinyl ethyl ether (7). Its stronger adsorbability than that of 3-ethoxyanhydroretinol (4) suggests the presence of more than one ethoxy group in the compound. The absence of any band characteristic of hydroxy group in the ir spectrum rules out the possibility of the presence of free hydroxy group but a strong band at 1 105 cm^{-1} strongly supports the presence of ethoxy group. The uv spectrum of the compound is similar to that of 3-hydroxyretinyl diester⁷ with a single maximum at 328 nm and its $SbCl_5$ product shows similar band at 670 nm. The 1H nmr spectrum (60 MHz; CCl_4) showed signals for all the protons including the deshielded methylene protons. Besides the weak molecular ion peak M^+ at m/z 358, the mass spectrum showed peaks at m/z 316 ($M^+ - 46$) and 266 (base peak, $M^+ - 92$) confirming the presence of two ethoxy groups. However, the lower fragmentation patterns are not clear. The hydroxy compound (8) derived from 7 showed a strong broad ir band at 3 320 cm^{-1} attributable to the hydroxy group. Available evidences indicate that the hydroxy compound is 3-hydroxyretinol (8). Further experimental evidences are essential to confirm the identity of 7 with that of 3-hydroxyretinyl diester isolated from fish liver oils⁷.

Henbest *et al.*⁴ suggested the scheme 1→4 for the formation of 3-ethoxyanhydroretinol (4). A reasonable pathway for the formation of 3-ethoxyretinyl ethyl ether (7) involves the steps: 1→2→5→6→7. The intermediate (5) is protonated at C-4 to give a carbonium ion at C-3 (6) which is finally converted to 7 by solvent ethanol.

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PMR Spectral Study of Steroidal Oxazolidinones

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OXAZOLIDINONES have been shown to possess various biological activities¹. This prompted us to undertake the synthesis and structural study of the steroidal diastereomeric oxazolidinones.

Reaction of 3 α ,4 α -epoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1)² in *N,N*-dimethyl formamide when refluxed with urea gave 6-nitrocholest-5-eno[4 α , 3 α -*d*]oxazolidin-2'-one (2) and 6-nitrocholest-5-eno[3 α , 4 α -*d*]oxazolidin-2'-one (3)³. The structures of these diastereomeric oxazolidinones were established on the basis of pmr spectral study.

The ir spectra of the oxazolidinones (2 and 3) exhibited characteristic bands at 3 420–3 490 and 1 715–1 725 cm^{-1} for oxazolidinone moiety⁴. In pmr spectra of 2 and 3, the NH proton appeared as slightly broad singlet at δ 7.74–8.01. The distinction between the two isomeric oxazolidinones 2 and 3 was made comparing the peak positions of C_3 and C_4 protons. Both $C_4\beta$ -proton (pseudo-axial) in 3 and $C_3\beta$ -proton (equatorial) in 2 are attached to oxygen-bearing carbon atoms, but $C_4\beta$ -proton in 3 though being axial (pseudo) appears downfield (δ 5.48)⁵ as compared to equatorial $C_3\beta$ -protons (δ 5.15) in 2. This is a reversal of the usual axial-equatorial relationship reported for a wide variety of six-membered ring system⁶. Similar observation was made regarding $C_4\beta$ -proton in 2 (pseudo-axial, δ 4.27) appearing at low-field than $C_3\beta$ -proton in 3 (equatorial, δ 3.98), both being attached to nitrogen-bearing carbon atoms. The low-field appearance of the pseudo-axial protons at C_4 can be attributed to its allylic nature and to the electron-withdrawing nitro group at C_6 .

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were determined on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer, and pmr spectra ($CDCl_3$) on a Varian A60 instrument with tetramethyl silane as the internal standard. Tlc plates were prepared from silica gel G and sprayed with 20% aqueous perchloric acid. Light petroleum refers to a fraction